

LANGUAGE AND CULTURAL COMPONENTS

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Summary

Cultural methods and research apparatus allow us to follow the development of the cultural language component operating within different levels of language units, to conclude that the combination of language and culture may have different configurations of a different nature. The thesis summarizes new approaches to language and cultural components.

Keywords: language, culture, methods, human mind, cognition.

The main concepts of cognitive linguistics are the concept of information and its processing by the human mind, the concept of knowledge structure and their representation in the human mind and language forms. Together with cognitive linguistics, cognitive psychology, and cognitive sociology, which make up cognition, it seeks to answer questions such as how the human mind is organized in principle, how man learns the world, what information about the world becomes knowledge, and what mental spaces are and in the next stage all the attention turns to culture and man. In this case, it is necessary to answer many questions, including: how does a person see the world, what is the role of metaphors and symbols? What is the role of phraseological units preserved in language and culture for centuries, and why is it so important for a person? Linguoculturology studies language as a cultural phenomenon. It is a certain vision of the world through the prism of the national language, when it plays the role of an expression of a particular national mentality. All linguistics is full of cultural and historical content, because the subject is the language that is the condition, basis and product of culture.

The foundations of the new philosophy of language, in which a comprehensive integrative approach has led to the essential interaction of many (not only related) sciences, are conditioned both by the internal logic of the development of linguistic research thought, and by general scientific and extralinguistic reasons that give rise to the formulation of new scientific problems, the search for new scientific methods, the formation of new scientific directions.

Linguoculturology is aimed at scrutinizing linguistic units in connection with historical and social development of the country at different periods and thus ensures general broad comprehension of the language as a complex system. [1]

The most important concepts for this collective work are those with which cultural information can be represented in linguistic units: cultural semes, cultural background, cultural concepts and cultural connotations. Its goal is to study the ways in which language embodies in its units, preserves and transmits culture. According to V.Telia, the tasks of linguoculturology include the study and description of the relationship between language and culture, language and ethnicity, language and folk mentality.

Different scientific schools consider the relationship between language and culture in different ways, but almost all recognize that culture and language are inextricably linked, as evidenced by the works of scientists: V.Humboldt, L.Wintgenstein, E.Sapir, B.Whorf, D. Fodor, P.O.Yakobson, I.A.Baudouin de Courtenay, A. A. Potebni, L. S. Vygotsky, V.A. Maslova, Yu.E.Prokhorov, N.I. Zhinkin, N.I.Tolstoy, Yu.M.Lotman, A.Vezhbitskaya, V.N.Telia, V.G. Kostomarova, E.M.Vereshchagin, G.A. D. Arutyunova, N.V.Ufimtseva and many other researchers.

In the analysis of the internal form of a word in linguistics, two trends are observed: the diachronic etymological interpretation of this concept and the state of synchronization of the internal form of language units with their content. [2]

When characterizing the linguo-cultural situation, two factors are important:

1) temporary: the linguo-cultural situation is understood as a constantly changing process, prepared by previous periods and preparing the basis for subsequent periods;

2) structural: the linguo-cultural situation contains a certain number of social formations, languages, and cultures.[3]

Recognition of the existence of a cultural component is important for addressing the link between language, culture and thought. The importance and relevance of research in this area emerges in the process of studying the cultural characteristics of language units that emphasize the difference in consciousness, cognition and worldview.

Literature

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